

Sustainable extraction of V and Ti from low-grade V-bearing titanomagnetite deposits

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Introduction

Vanadium (V) and titanium (Ti) are important strategic/critical raw materials (CRMs) that are widely used in many advanced products and industrial sectors due to their excellent physical and chemical properties (Zhu et al., 2023). Titanium is primarily extracted from minerals such as rutile (TiO_2) and ilmenite (FeTiO_3), while vanadium is commonly obtained from vanadium-bearing titanomagnetite (VTM) deposits, rich in V, Ti, Fe, as well as trace elements (Wang et al., 2025). Global titanium reserves are estimated at around 800 million tons, with high-quality rutile accounting for only 6% (USGS, 2025). As the grade of ores containing rutile currently declines, ilmenite (94%) has become the primary titanium source. On the other hand, global VTM reserves are estimated at 60 billion tons, far exceeding Ti-rich oxide deposits containing ilmenite and rutile.

Materials and methods

In order to meet Europe's Critical Raw Materials Act (CRMA) benchmark of 10% domestic extraction and reduce its reliance on imported V and Ti, the AVANTIS HE project aims to develop a near-zero-waste, multi-metal extraction process for Europe's low grade un-exploited resources such as VTM deposits and mining wastes i.e. historical & fresh V/Ti-bearing tailings (AVANTIS, 2025). With this low-carbon, cost-effective, and responsible mining approach the projects aims to sustainably produce V and Ti pre-concentrates, which can be further refined into high-purity Ti metal and V_2O_5 , facilitating efficient resource use and minimizing environmental impact. In this sense, this integrated approach involves i) life cycle assessment (LCA) to evaluate the environmental impacts of V and Ti metal production on human health, ecosystems, and resources, ii) techno-economic assessment (TEA) to evaluate the economic viability of tailored combinations of the next-generation, low-carbon mining and beneficiation technologies over their operational lifetime, and iii) public acceptance (PA) / social license to operate (SLO) to assess the level of community acceptance with respect to land use, local conditions and other sensitive issues for the extraction of V and Ti from European resources (Figure 1) (Komnitsas and Eerola, 2024).

Figure 1. Integrated framework to evaluate sustainable extraction of V and Ti from low-grade VTM resources in Europe in the framework of the AVANTIS HE project

Results and discussion

This integrated framework will offer a comprehensive evaluation of the newly developed mining approach, which incorporates innovative selective blasting, fragmentation, and pre-concentration technologies such as bulk ore sorting, advanced flotation and magnetic separation to process complex, low-grade domestic V/Ti-bearing resource deposits that are currently not economically viable. Furthermore, it will maximize the V/Ti potential of Europe's low-grade, complex VTM deposits, reinforcing the EU's position in the V and Ti value chain enhancing resource sustainability, economic resilience, and technological innovation.

Special emphasis is also given, apart from reducing energy requirements, greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and the overall footprint of V- and Ti- extraction, on health and safety (H&S) aspects. In this context, geochemical studies are performed to assess environmental and human health impacts of PHEs present in the processing chain. Leaching (pH-dependence and kinetic) tests are carried out to assess the potential release of elements and define possible management options (e.g., recycling, treatment, disposal). Human health-risk assessment is also implemented with the application of bioaccessibility tests (Komnitsas et al., 2025; Vathi and Komnitsas, 2025).

Conclusions

In this study, the sustainable extraction of V and Ti from low-grade European VTM ores using a wide range of low-carbon, near-zero-waste technologies is assessed. Through the integration of environmental, economic, and social assessments, it aims to reduce EU import dependency, unlock domestic resources, and support the strategic goals of the recent CRMA.

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